

Early Childhood Sleep Problems and Later Cognitive Human Capital

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ABSTRACT

Objective: To analyse the relationship and underlying mechanism between early sleep problems and later cognitive outcomes. We use a structured life course approach to compare hypotheses about the timing and pattern of exposure to sleep problems to predict later cognition.

Introduction: Fetal period and first 1000 days of life shape life cycle health and skill formation (Almond and Currie, 2011). Shocks in early childhood can have negative and heterogeneous effects. Sleep moderates stress/shocks, replenishing the brain, thereby the cognitive and non-cognitive capabilities. Despite the abundance of human capital studies, the single activity that humans resort to—sleeping—has received very little attention in economics literature (Jin & Zeibarth, 2018). In this paper, we contribute to human capital literature by looking at the role of sleep quality & underlying mechanism of this empirical effect in children.

Methods: We use ALSPAC data, a prospective birth cohort of 14500 pregnant women and families based in Avon, UK for our study. Children's sleep quality defined as 'continuously gets up after few hours of sleep' is measured at 18, 24, 42, 57, 69, 81 and 108 months of age. The outcomes are Maths grade at age 4 and 7, Reading score at age 7, IQ and Mathematical Reasoning score at age 8, NARA Comprehension and Accuracy scores at age 9. We used logistic models to identify critical periods, sensitive periods and cumulative effects across childhood adjusting for child, family and prenatal covariates. The Bayesian Information Criterion (BIC) compares the fit across the above three models representing life course patterns of exposure to sleep problems. Next, we assume that non-cognitive outcomes including behavioural difficulties at 81 months of age are affected by sleep problems at 18-57 months to produce treatment effect in cognition at 9 years. Following Heckman and Pinto (2015), we use Oaxaca decomposition, which decomposes the “treatment effect” of high-dose sleep problems into non-cognitive outcomes and unobservables to explain the difference in outcomes between treatment & control group.

Results: We do not identify any critical periods but identified 24 months of age as a sensitive period for some outcomes for which adverse effects of poor sleep is the largest. Cumulative sleep problems offered the best fit and a linear dose-response relationship between the two exists for all outcomes, with larger effect for IQ. Further, behavioural difficulties in mid-childhood explain more than one-third of the later cognition penalty between children with early poor and better sleep quality. In a subgroup analysis, prenatal depression is identified as a risk factor.

Discussion: Quantifying the cognitive penalty of poor sleep allows us to measure the social cost of childhood sleep problems. The findings imply that cumulative sleep problems along with a sensitive period at 24 months may have the worst effect on cognition. Moreover, knowledge of the production function of cognition is important in policy making as efficiency is achieved by reallocating resources from later to earlier in the life cycle. Further we identify prenatal depression as a source of parental disinvestment, exacerbating the adverse effects of poor sleep in childhood.